

Placeholder Name of the conference

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“As a [researcher], I [want to find open educational resources about data literacy] by using a [knowledge graph based search platform].”

Use cases and user stories for the development of the DALIA platform

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Abstract

In today’s digital society, the ability to handle, understand, and manage data in an efficient way is increasingly recognized as a fundamental skill across all disciplines. The DALIA project (DATA LIteracy Alliance [1]) aims to foster data literacy by providing high-quality, openly accessible educational resources (OER). These materials are designed to meet the diverse needs of learners and professionals at various educational levels, levels of RDM experience, and disciplinary backgrounds. The resources are contributed by a wide range of institutions, including the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) consortia, national Research Data Management (RDM) initiatives, data competence centers, and other stakeholders from the research and education landscape. To enable efficient access and use of these learning materials, DALIA is developing a knowledge graph that supports semantic linking and integration, adhering to the FAIR principles—Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable [2,3].

A central element of the DALIA platform development is the implementation of an agile, user-centred approach. Core to this methodology are user stories, which articulate specific user needs and expectations in a structured, scenario-based format [4]. Each user story is framed as: “As a [role with specific RDM experience], I have the [need/requirement] to be fulfilled by a [knowledge base function].” This format ensures that requirements are clearly linked to both the user context and the intended system functionality, while maintaining cross-disciplinary applicability.

Based on these user stories, more detailed use cases are developed, specifying triggers, user actions, system responses, expected outcomes, and acceptance criteria. These use cases guide the iterative design and development of the platform and ensure alignment with real-world needs. The user stories encompass both, the perspectives of learners—seeking relevant learning materials—and contributors, who wish to publish content, share feedback, or access usage reports.

The initial set of user stories was developed by combining general community input and a structured community workshop. Participants were invited to describe their needs via a targeted survey, considering their role, educational level, specialization, and intended use of the platform. This participatory process enabled the integration of a wide range of perspectives and ensured that the platform supports diverse usage scenarios. Through continuous refinement of user stories and active community involvement, DALIA remains adaptive, inclusive, and responsive to evolving user needs in the field of research data management and data literacy.

With the use cases, we not only demonstrate a useful development tool for improving the DALIA search portal, but also one to take the needs and requirements of the user community into account, which are an important stakeholder group for DALIA.

Keywords: Use Case, User Story, Data Literacy, Search Platform

Resources

DALIA Search Platform. <https://search.dalia.education/basic> "Search platform for OER regarding data literacy"

Author contributions

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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